

Women's Rights and Legitimate Interests

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Over the years of its independent development, Uzbekistan has achieved significant success in protecting the rights and legitimate interests of women. No less significant are the achievements in ensuring their active participation in the socio-political and socio-economic life of the country. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan also highly values human dignity and places particular emphasis on gender equality.

Specifically, Article 58 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "women and men have equal rights." It is worth noting that the legal foundations of gender equality are reflected in international and national legislation. Specifically, the equality of men and women is also recognized in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1948.

Experience shows that in an economically stable society, equality between men and women is ensured at a high level. A person's professional development has distinct phases; at any level of professional development, no matter how complex an individual's actual behavior, there is a complex interconnection and interdependence between social parameters (requirements) and the transformation of the individual's inner world. Although the boundaries between "female" and "male" professions are blurred in the modern world, there are unspoken requirements for both. Women working in law enforcement must be able to combine the incompatible. They must possess a strong yet gentle character. This is largely true for women working in the juvenile department. They must manage to help their children overcome their problems while also caring for their own families.

The issue of women serving in law enforcement agencies is highly relevant. A

significant number of studies by foreign scholars actively explore ways to address the problem of how female police officers can combine professional, family, and other social responsibilities. Female law enforcement officers are better at navigating social situations than civilians, and they are more perceptive about the actions and motives of others. These personal qualities of female police officers may be a consequence of their professional skills and are quite common in interactions with detainees in situations where suspects attempt to mislead law enforcement officers and when it is necessary to establish the true motives of their behavior (e.g., when resisting, behaving inappropriately, etc.).

The Ministry of Internal Affairs has created 360 female inspector positions to work with women in need of legal and social assistance. To ensure prompt and effective support for women who have suffered harassment and violence, standard operating procedures for a joint response to gender-based violence have been developed and implemented for law enforcement, healthcare, and social and psychological professionals.

Consistent and comprehensive reforms have ensured economic stability. To systematically implement the UN Sustainable Development Goals, our country has adopted the "National Goals and Targets of Uzbekistan for Sustainable Development until 2030". The fifth goal in this document is "Ensuring gender equality and empowering all women." This, in turn, includes economic, social, legal, and other measures. All government agencies and organizations, institutions, and public organizations of national significance are responsible for achieving these goals. As we know, on March 20, 2019, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan put forward five important initiatives to organize work in the social, spiritual, and educational spheres. The fifth initiative is aimed at addressing the issue of women's employment and creating fulfilling living conditions for women by providing them with jobs.

With government support, the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan organizes free retraining and training courses for new specialties. Centers are being opened where women from rural areas learn artistic crafts and trades, such as carpet weaving, yarn dyeing, and

other skills that provide them with additional income opportunities. Discussing the share of women in employment, which has now increased to 44%, a significant increase in their participation in small businesses was emphasized. Today, 35% of businesses are founded and headed by women.

Delegates from UN member states and human rights organizations were also informed that women predominate in the overall employment structure in Uzbekistan in sectors such as healthcare and sports (82%), education, culture, art, and science (72%), and trade and catering (54%). It's worth noting that the Republic has also prepared a draft National Action Plan, as noted by Tanzila Narbaeva, Chairperson of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, at the opening of the roundtable. "Actively promoting women's participation in the political, economic, and social life of Uzbekistan is a key task for the government," said Tanzila Narbaeva. This is confirmed by the recent decisions taken by Uzbekistan's leadership aimed at significantly increasing the role of women in decision-making processes that are vital to the country's future development.

Uzbekistan is taking steps to implement the Sustainable Development Goals by increasing women's participation in public and state development, ensuring gender equality, and preventing discrimination against women. This was noted by Akmal Saidov, First Deputy Speaker of the Legislative Chamber of the Parliament and Director of the National Human Rights Center. He emphasized that the draft National Action Plan on Women, Peace, and Security identifies priority areas for change, implementing more effective gender policies, and striving to achieve results.

The draft National Action Plan on Women, Peace, and Security of Uzbekistan includes:

- Encouraging women's participation in peace and security processes; Widespread dissemination of knowledge on the topic of "Women, Peace, and Security," including among decision-makers;
- Systems for protecting and addressing the special needs of women and girls in

emergency situations;

- Civil society participation in the implementation of UN Security Council Resolution 1325 on women, peace, and security.

At the core of Resolution 1325 is the recognition that lasting peace cannot be achieved without the significant participation of women in conflict prevention, resolution, and peacebuilding. The document calls for the full and equal participation of women in all peace and security initiatives, along with the mainstreaming of gender issues. This includes increasing women's participation in peace negotiations to resolve conflicts, as well as increasing the number of women in leadership positions at both the international and national levels.

Special attention was paid to informing the international community about the successes of women's employment in the country. It was noted that targeted government measures to employ graduates of secondary specialized vocational schools are yielding significant results. Programs aimed at improving working and educational conditions for women, particularly in rural areas, and engaging them in entrepreneurship are developed and implemented annually. In recent years, more than 327,000 women have received preferential loans totaling 7.4 trillion soums to develop women's entrepreneurship.

In 2021, approximately 1.4 trillion soums are planned to be allocated to women entrepreneurs from the Fund for Reconstruction and Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

As a result, over the past four years, more than 620,200 women have been employed, and 106,000 have been assisted in establishing private businesses. For example, in 2020 alone, approximately 126,000 women were provided with preferential loans under the "Every Family – Entrepreneur" program. Nearly 215,000 families received loans for the development of family businesses totaling over six trillion soums. As part of the Five Important Initiatives, sewing workshops have been established in remote areas, providing employment to 10,000 women.

These results were achieved through a comprehensive approach that created not only a solid legal foundation but also an effective institutional framework. One example is the establishment of a public organization, the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan, which has become a productive mechanism for supporting this segment of the population and protecting their rights and legitimate interests.